

Given the example of a dashboard, how would using one add value to your work?

28 Responses

Help debate which package to use

Choosing right tools

Better tracking data for more accurate future estimations

Determining backlog

Find packages I had not heard of

Choice of tool

Save time on manually generating stats for a package

Good to get a snapshot at the beginning of a consultancy

Feed to AI bot to help improve sustainability

Given the example of a dashboard, how would using one add value to your work?

28 Responses

Quick assessment of potential dependencies

Applies more pressure to develop sustainable software outside of group

sharing and discussion

Determine projects to contribute to

Make it work for non python projects

Highlight shortcomings in packages I maintain

Choosing between packages that do similar jobs

Evaluate package health and code base in need of updating/improving

identify risk areas (eg all contributors in single org)

Given the example of a dashboard, how would using one add value to your work?

28 Responses

Understand if any projects are languishing or rotted

Use as argument for funders to support

Evidencing package use/impact for grants

Not reinventing the wheel

collect info at a glance

Understand / show how sustainable our week is

Demonstrate sustainability and project health to funders

Just double-checking we havent missed anything before official deployment

Audit tools used in existing projects - move on from not well-maintained packages

Given the example of a dashboard, how would using one add value to your work?

28 Responses

standardize metrics (if other projects
use the same stats)